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Neuroendocrinology Pseudo-diabetes due to Oshtoran Syndrome

Abstract

Oshtoran Syndrome, also known as H63D Syndrome Type-3. This rare systemic medical condition is characterized by a cascading progression of various disease processes, leading to a very dangerously broad variety autonomic dysfunctions and consequential structural organ damages. One of its most dangerous aspect is the potential development of a pseudo-diabetes which can lead to a lethal outcome if not recognizes as what is truly is.

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Oshtoran Syndrome

Among all rare diseases Oshtoran Syndrome is one of the most insidious, primarily rooted in PANS syndrome, rheumatic fever, or similar conditions experienced during early life stages. These initial conditions may instigate clinical features of a secondary H63D syndrome in individuals bearing a homozygous H63D mutation which must not be confused with hemochromatosis. After a while H63D syndrome's NTBI accumulation effects lead to extensive mitochondrial dysfunction and autonomic dysregulation across multiple organ systems. The pathology of Oshtoran Syndrome entails autonomic dysfunction within the central nervous system (CNS), autonomic nervous system (ANS), and the innate immune system, especially pronounced in advanced disease stages. Patients may exhibit a wide spectrum of neurologic, endocrinological, and immunologic disorders. Notable symptoms include neuropsychiatric manifestations, motor impairments akin to non-motor Parkinson's symptoms, cognitive impairment, atypical motor and perceptual disturbances, tic disorders, and the slow degeneration of the substantia nigra. Diagnostically, elevated levels of certain blood and urine parameters like eosinophils, basophils, kynurenine, kynurenine acid, TRY/KYN ratio, (nor-)epinephrine, and other catecholamines as well as cortisol are observed. Imaging might reveal fatty changes in the liver along with nodular hyperplasia (FNH). The syndrome was initially studied in Iran and traces back to an Iranian patient and her descendants from the Zagros Mountains. It garnered renewed attention in 2017 when the Marvel entertainment company used Oshtoran Syndrome excessively as a fate determining illness in its "Spider-Man" PS4 entertainment products. In the academic realm Oshtoran Syndrome experienced quite some limelight in

2022/2023 through the efforts of a research team led by H63D pioneer researcher Jacob Adams. The very complex pathogenesis of Oshtoran Syndrome encompasses a blend of genetic disorders, mitochondrial dysfunction, and disorders of kynurenine metabolism. Currently, Oshtoran Syndrome remains incurable, albeit to some extent treatable. Treatment primarily revolves around anti-inflammatory therapies, calming down the body's alarm systems (catecholamines) and address symptoms in order to improve the quality of life of those affected. An interdisciplinary approach is deemed critical, balancing symptom management with long-term pharmaceutical strategies to enhance patient outcomes.

Details

The underlying pathophysiology of Oshtoran Syndrome is complex and not yet fully understood. However, it is known to emerge from dysfunctional immune system processes, primarily rooted in PANS syndrome, rheumatic fever, or similar conditions experienced during early life stages. These initial conditions may instigate clinical features of a secondary H63D syndrome in individuals bearing a homozygous H63D mutation. This leads to extensive mitochondrial dysfunction due to damages caused by NTBI and autonomic dysregulation across multiple organ systems. The pathology entails autonomic dysfunction within the CNS, ANS, and the innate immune system, especially pronounced in advanced disease stages. Patients with Oshtoran Syndrome may exhibit a very wide range of symptoms, including neuropsychiatric manifestations, non-motor impairments akin to Parkinson's symptoms, cognitive impairment, idiosyncratic motor and perceptual disturbances, tic disorders, and degeneration of the substantia nigra. Elevated levels of certain blood and urine parameters like eosinophils, basophils, kynurenine, kynurenine acid and TRY/KYN ratio, bilirubin, especially important high levels of epinephrine, norepinephrine, and catecholamines are observed. Imaging might reveal fatty changes in the liver along with nodular hyperplasia (FNH).

Diagnostic Challenges

Early diagnosis of the syndrome is, as utmost important as it is, notably challenging due to its

complex and multifaceted symptomatology. Indicators such as unexplained liver disease, neurological and/or neuropsychiatric symptoms, and a shift in the tryptophan/kynurenine ratio could herald the presence of this rare syndrome, especially if they manifest following a sudden onset of disease during childhood or adolescence. Upon detection of these alarm signs, a comprehensive diagnostic workup is initiated, necessitating an interdisciplinary approach.

Treatment Modalities

Currently, Oshtoran Syndrome remains incurable, albeit treatable. Treatment primarily revolves around anti-inflammatory and symptomatic pharmacological therapies. An interdisciplinary approach is critical, balancing symptom management with long-term therapeutic strategies to enhance patient outcomes. Future research aims to unravel the underlying mechanisms of Oshtoran Syndrome to devise effective therapeutic interventions, thereby ameliorating the quality and expectancy of life for the afflicted individuals. Until now, at least two composite medications of older compounds (designed by using already fully licensed medical drugs) have been made available for patients suffering from Oshtoran Syndrome. One is Amitradicain, developed by Dr. Ali Asgari on request and with the support of the International H63D Syndrome Research Consortium, Amitradicain is a patent-free medication blended together to alleviate the chaotic signal transmission from the nervous system to the organs via innervation. In this regards the medication has shown robust efficacy in a series of individual treatment trials. It is not produced by the pharmaceutical industry but is prepared directly in pharmacies, following the specialized doctor's formula. Due to its side effect profile, treatment should commence in a hospital setting for patients with heart conditions, obesity, respiratory issues, or other severe symptoms. Despite its high risk profile, Amitradicain holds high hopes for improving the quality of life for those afflicted with Oshtoran Syndrome. Amitradil, and Travastil on the other hand, are related and entirely patent-free compost-pharmaceuticals to Amitradicain without procain for those patients whose heart and blood sugar regulation has already become affected by the consequences of Oshtoran Syndrome.

Pseudo-diabetes due to autonomic dysfunction caused by Oshtoran Syndrome

Autonomic dysfunction and metabolism is one of the strongest hallmark of advanced states of Oshtoran Syndrome, and among these the development of pseudo-diabetes is one of many severe and dangerous direct consequences of Oshtoran Syndrome.

The autonomic nervous system (ANS) plays a vital role in regulating metabolic processes, including glucose homeostasis. In Oshtoran Syndrome, autonomic dysfunction can lead to aberrant signaling, affecting various metabolic pathways. Mitochondrial issues can lead to impaired pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH) function and anaerobic glycolysis, resulting in a “masked” ATP shortage. This can elevate lactate levels, further exacerbating metabolic imbalances. The dysfunctional ANS may misinterpret ATP shortage, even when masked, e.g. due to elevated lactate levels as indicators of impending hypoglycemia. This can trigger the liver to initiate gluconeogenesis even when blood sugar levels are already high, leading to an even higher hyperglycemia.

This creates a vicious cycle: the “misinformed” liver, responding to false signals, produces more glucose, exacerbating hyperglycemia. The dysfunctional ANS continues to misinterpret metabolic markers, perpetuating the cycle and leading to severe metabolic imbalances. Understanding such complex interplays is absolutely crucial for managing Oshtoran Syndrome. Therapeutic interventions may need to target not just the autonomic dysfunction but also the metabolic pathways involved. This often involves unorthodox approaches like a pharmacological meta-agent like Amitradicain, which moderates autonomic signaling down, along with metabolic modulators that in some patients corrects the underlying mitochondrial dysfunction and glucose imbalances. Anti-diabetic medications aim to lower blood sugar levels. If these medications are administered under the false assumption that the patient has diabetes, they can exacerbate the already complex metabolic imbalances. The liver, already synthesizing glucose in response to false signals from the dysfunctional autonomic

nervous system, may be further stimulated to produce glucose, leading the patient to take an extra bolus shot of insulin (or his/her other blood lowering drugs which might be recognized by the ANS as a further signal for a pre-hypoglycemic situation. As a consequence the liver will get the next ANS order (simplified) via the innervation network and produce again more glucose, “trusting” the orders of the ANS. However, there might have been a sudden drop in blood sugar levels, however in the diabetic range.

Anti-diabetic medications often work by improving insulin sensitivity or increasing insulin production. In the context of Oshtoran Syndrome, where the issue is not insulin resistance but rather a complex interplay of autonomic and metabolic dysfunction, these medications can worsen the existing metabolic imbalance, way up to lethal outcomes. If there is no CGM measurement used or the data is interpreted wrongly the entire preventable disaster could be stopped by lowering the

Amplification of Autonomic Dysfunction

The autonomic dysfunction characteristic of Oshtoran Syndrome may interpret the drug-induced hypoglycemia as a crisis, further amplifying the dysfunctional signaling. This can lead to a range of symptoms, from palpitations and sweating to severe neurological symptoms.

Persistent hypoglycemia and metabolic imbalances can lead to multi-organ damage over time. Organs like the kidneys, liver, and heart may be particularly vulnerable. Patients with Oshtoran Syndrome are often on multiple medications to manage various symptoms. Adding anti-diabetic medications to the mix increases the risk of drug interactions, which can have unpredictable and potentially severe consequences. Misdiagnosis and inappropriate treatment can lead to loss of trust in healthcare providers and can be emotionally distressing for the patient and their family. It also raises ethical questions about the quality of care provided. This underscores the importance of an accurate diagnosis, particularly in complex, multi-systemic conditions like Oshtoran Syndrome. A thorough understanding of the underlying pathophysiology is crucial for effective

management and to avoid the pitfalls of misdiagnosis and inappropriate treatment. CGM provides real-time, high-resolution data on glucose levels, allowing for the identification of patterns that are not apparent in standard, intermittent blood glucose testing. In the context of Oshtoran Syndrome, this can reveal the unique glucose dynamics that you described—plateaus or sudden spikes in glucose levels without corresponding food or drink intake.

Unmasking Pseudo-Diabetes

The patterns detected by CGM can serve as a “signature” for the pseudo-diabetes seen in Oshtoran Syndrome. Unlike typical diabetes, where glucose levels correlate with food intake and insulin levels, the erratic glucose levels in Oshtoran Syndrome are driven by autonomic dysfunction and false activation of gluconeogenesis. This can be unmasked by longitudinal CGM data, which can show glucose levels spiking or plateauing independent of dietary intake. The interpretation of CGM data in this context requires a high level of expertise. Physicians need to be well-versed not just in endocrinology but also in neurology and autonomic dysfunction to correctly interpret the data. They must be able to distinguish between the glucose patterns seen in conventional diabetes and those seen in Oshtoran Syndrome, which requires a nuanced understanding of the underlying pathophysiology. Once the correct diagnosis is made, it can guide targeted therapy aimed at stabilizing autonomic function and metabolic pathways, rather than lowering glucose levels per se. This may help to prevent the catastrophic consequences of misdiagnosis and mistreatment. The utility of CGM in this context also has implications for research and clinical guidelines. It highlights the need for multi-disciplinary approaches to the diagnosis and management of complex, multi-system disorders like Oshtoran Syndrome. It also underscores the importance of incorporating advanced diagnostic tools like CGM into clinical guidelines for the diagnosis and management of suspected metabolic disorders. The use of advanced diagnostic tools like CGM also raises ethical considerations. Given the severe consequences of misdiagnosis, one

could argue that it is ethically imperative to employ such diagnostic tools in complex cases, despite the additional cost and complexity involved. In summary, CGM can be a game-changer in the diagnosis and management of Oshtoran Syndrome, potentially preventing severe morbidity and mortality associated with misdiagnosis. However, its utility is contingent on the expertise of the treating physicians and a healthcare system that supports multi-disciplinary, nuanced approaches to complex disorders.

Life threatening medication

The administration of standard diabetes treatments like Metformin and short-acting insulins to patients with Oshtoran Syndrome can indeed be life-threatening, and the consequences can be catastrophic. Here is a comprehensive look at why: Metformin, excessively used as a “safe” drug to treat Type 2 diabetes, can exacerbate the mitochondrial dysfunction inherent in Oshtoran Syndrome. It can lead to severe lactic acidosis, a life-threatening condition where the pH of the body drops dangerously low due to the accumulation of lactate. This is especially concerning given that patients with Oshtoran Syndrome already have a predisposition to elevated lactate levels due to mitochondrial dysfunction. Long and even short-acting insulins, and indeed all other anti-diabetic medications, pose a severe risk of hypoglycemia in these patients. The malfunctioning nervous system in Oshtoran Syndrome can send erratic signals to the pancreas to release endogenous insulin. When this endogenous insulin release is compounded by exogenous insulin administration, it can lead to severe, rapid-onset hypoglycemia.

Catastrophic Confluence

The situation becomes acutely life-threatening when these two factors - lactic acidosis from Metformin and severe hypoglycemia from insulin - occur simultaneously. The body is thrust into a metabolic crisis, with multiple systems failing concurrently. This can lead to a rapid deterioration in the patient’s condition, necessitating emergency interventions like mechanical ventilation, hemodialysis, and i.V. administration of high-concentration dextrose solutions. Despite these measures, the risk of a

lethal outcome remains exceedingly high. Administering standard diabetes treatments to Oshtoran Syndrome patients not only poses severe medical risks but also raises significant ethical and legal questions. It could be considered a grave medical error, potentially leading to malpractice lawsuits and severe reputational damage for the healthcare providers involved. This underscores the critical importance of specialized care for Oshtoran Syndrome patients. Clinicians must be well-versed in the unique metabolic and autonomic dysfunctions associated with the condition to avoid such catastrophic errors. Advanced diagnostic tools like continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) and specialized medications like Amitradil should definitely be considered standard care for these patients. In summary, the use of standard diabetes treatments in Oshtoran Syndrome patients is not just inappropriate; it's perilous, with the potential for catastrophic outcomes.

Conclusion

The administration of any standard diabetes treatment to patients with Oshtoran Syndrome can have catastrophic, life-threatening consequences. Metformin can exacerbate existing mitochondrial dysfunction, leading to severe lactic acidosis. All insulins and other anti-diabetic medications can induce rapid-onset, severe hypoglycemia due to the syndrome's inherent autonomic dysfunction. The simultaneous occurrence of lactic acidosis and severe hypoglycemia can thrust the body into a metabolic crisis, leading to multi-system failure and an exceedingly high risk of mortality. This highlights the critical need for specialized, individualized care for Oshtoran Syndrome patients, including the use of advanced diagnostic tools like CGM and specialized meta-composite medications like Amitradil. The situation also raises significant ethical and legal questions, emphasizing the importance of accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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References

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